

ASSESSMENT OF MICROBIAL QUALITY OF FISH MARKETED IN DISTRICT LAHORE, PAKISTAN

Zahid Sharif Mirza¹, Suman Riaz², Usman Elahi², Javairia Shafi^{1*}

¹Fisheries Research and Training Institute, Manawan, Lahore, Pakistan.

²Department of Biological Sciences, Superior University, Lahore, Pakistan.

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 09/09/2024.

Accepted: 13/10/2024.

Published: 16/10/2024.

Keywords:

Fish Quality,
Traditional Vendors,
Superstores, Total Plate
Count, Total Coliform,
Fecal Coliform

Author info:

Corresponding Author.

Javairia Shafi

javairiamalik@gmail.com

Citation:

Zahid Sharif Mirza, Suman Riaz, Usman Elahi, & Javairia Shafi. (2024). ASSESSMENT OF MICROBIAL QUALITY OF FISH MARKETED IN DISTRICT LAHORE, PAKISTAN. Pakistan's Multidisciplinary Journal for Arts & Science, 5(3), 1–10.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13944748>

DOI:

<https://10.5281/zenodo.13944748>

ABSTRACT

Determination of the microbial quality of food fish is essential to understand the potential health risks associated with fish consumption. Present study was conducted to assesses the microbial quality of fish procured from conventional vendors and superstores randomly selected from different zones of Lahore. Forty-three (43) samples of three different fish species; *Labeo rohita*, *Oreochromis niloticus* and *Wallagu attu*, were collected from six zones of Lahore to determine their microbial quality in terms of total plate count, total coliform, fecal coliform, and *E. coli*. Results indicated that 9.30% of samples exceeded permissible limits for total coliform. Highest total plate count (16.45 ± 9.66) $\times 10^3$ cfu.g⁻¹) was recorded in fish from the Nishtar zone. Fish samples collected from the Gulberg zone showed the highest counts for fecal coliform and *E. coli* (60.51 ± 49.96 MPN.g⁻¹ and 36.03 ± 25.58 MPN.g⁻¹, respectively). Fish from traditional vendors exhibited microbial loads 150% higher than those from superstores, suggesting better hygiene practices in larger retail environments. These findings highlight critical concerns regarding food safety and hygiene practices in Lahore's fish markets, emphasizing the need for improved regulatory oversight and targeted interventions. This research contributes to the understanding of microbial risks associated with fish consumption and underscores the importance of ongoing monitoring to safeguard public health.

INTRODUCTION.

Hunger and malnutrition remain critical global issues, impacting millions of people around the world (Unicef, 2021). While progress from 1990 to 2015 reduced chronic hunger by 17%, recent data show an increase, with 815 million people impacted in 2016. Addressing this, the strategy to eradicate hunger by 2030 emphasizes sustainable agriculture and food systems ((FAO, 2022). Often overlooked, fish and fisheries are crucial for food and nutrition security, especially in low- and middle-income countries (Hasselberg et al., 2020). Fish accounts for 7% of global protein consumption and 17% of animal protein intake. It is a key source of long-chain omega-3 highly unsaturated fatty acids (HUFAs), such as EPA and DHA, which offer numerous health benefits. Fish is also a rich source of vital micronutrients, including iron, zinc, and selenium. Its nutritional components support cognitive development, prevent stunting, improve maternal and child health, boost immunity, and reduce the risk of cardiovascular disease (Maulu et al., 2021). However, nutritional composition of fish renders it highly susceptible to microbial spoilage. Fish spoilage starts immediately after its harvest, and its rate depends on several factors including postharvest handling and fish species (Shafi et al., 2020).

In recent decades, there has been a significant global shift in fish consumption patterns, with per capita consumption rising steadily from 12.5 kg in the 1980s to 20.5 kg in 2017 (FAO, 2022; Ljusenius et al., 2020). In Pakistan, several initiatives have been taken at national level to increase consumption of fish/ seafood. In Punjab (Pakistan), most fish markets lack appropriate frozen storage facilities and have poor hygienic conditions. In most of the cases, temperature of the fish during transportation and marketing remains higher than 0° C leading to microbial and chemical spoilage (Sharif et al., 2014). The present study was, therefore, conducted to comprehensively evaluate the microbial quality of raw edible fish available in the markets of Lahore. This research is crucial for informing public health policies and practices aimed at minimizing the risks associated with consuming raw fish and ensuring the well-being of consumers in Lahore.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Sample Collection

Forty-three (43) whole samples of *Labeo rohita*, *Orochromis niloticus* and *Wallago attu* were randomly collected from the markets located in six zones of Lahore (Figure 1). Fish samples were collected from two types of vendors; superstores and tradition vendors including market retailers and street vendors. Collected fish samples, packed individually in sterilized bags and stored in ice boxes, were transported to the Quality Control Laboratories (QCL) at Fisheries Research & Training Institute, Lahore. Fish samples were stored at -18 °C till analysis.

Figure 1: Schematic presentation of research activities

Sample Analysis

For determination of microbial quality of fish, fish flesh was collected from the ventral muscles of collected samples. Analytical methods outlined in AOAC (2023) and BAM (FDA, 2023) were used for determination of Total Plate Count (TPC), Total Coliform (TC), Fecal Coliform (FC) and *E. coli* in fish samples. In order to prepare serial dilutions from fish samples, 50 g sample was homogenized with sterile Butterfield's buffer solution (450 mL). For determination of total plate count, dilutions were incubated at 35 °C for 48 h after mixing with molten plate count agar. Plates with 25 -250 colonies were counted and reported as cfu/g. In order to find total coliform and fecal coliform, dilutions in test tubes were incubated at 35 °C for 48 h after mixing with lauryl tryptose broth. From gas positive tubes, a loopful of suspension was transferred to test tubes containing brilliant green lactose broth test tubes and *E. coli* broth each; which were then incubated at 35 °C for 48 h. The Most Probable Number (MPN) for Total Coliforms and Fecal Coliforms was determined based on the number of gas-positive tubes using brilliant green lactose broth for TC and *E. coli* broth for FC. For determination of *E. coli* count, Levine's eosin -methylene blue agar plates were streaked with a loopful of suspension from cultures with positive reaction in *E. coli* medium. The *E. coli* count was determined by re-inoculating suspected colonies from Levine's eosin-methylene blue agar plates into tryptone water, and the results were expressed as MPN/g (AOAC, 2023; FDA, 2023).

Statistical Analysis

Data of microbial parameters of fish samples has been compiled through descriptive statistics. One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by post hoc analysis using Tukey's Test was employed to identify significant differences in microbial parameters among samples from different fish species and various zones of Lahore. All statistical analysis was two tailed and with .05 significance level.

RESULTS

Microbial quality parameters of 43 fish samples of three fish species collected from different areas of Lahore are presented in Table 1. Total plate count varied from $0.590 \times 10^3 - 93.0 \times 10^3$ cfu.g⁻¹ for *L. rohita*, $0.22 \times 10^3 - 42.0 \times 10^3$ cfu.g⁻¹ for *O. niloticus* and $0.24 \times 10^3 - 22.0 \times 10^3$ cfu.g⁻¹ for *W. attu*. Total coliform, fecal coliform and *E. coli* in the fish samples varied from $3.60 - >1100$ MPN.g⁻¹, $<3.0 - 460.0$ MPN.g⁻¹, and $<3.0 - 210.0$ MPN.g⁻¹ respectively. Samples of *L. rohita* showed the highest total plate count ($(10.80 \pm 5.96) \times 10^3$ MPN.g⁻¹), while *W. attu* had the least ($(5.24 \pm 1.80) \times 10^3$ MPN.g⁻¹). Highest total coliform was found in *L. rohita* followed by *W. attu* and *O. niloticus*. Highest count of fecal coliform was, however, recorded in *W. attu* followed by *L. rohita* and *O. niloticus*. Similar trend was observed for *E. coli*. The difference in microbial parameters of three fish species, was, however, not significant.

Figure 2: Microbial parameters of fish samples collected from six zones of Lahore; [a] Total Plate Count, [b] Total Coliform, [c] Fecal Coliform, [d] *E. coli*. Red line in [b] and [c] indicates the permissible limit

Figure 2 shows the comparison of microbial parameters of fish collected from six zones of Lahore. Samples collected from Nishter zone showed highest total plate count ($(16.45 \pm 9.66) \times 10^3$ cfu.g⁻¹). Average total plate count of fish collected from different zones decreased in the following order; Nishter > Aziz Bhatti > Allama Iqbal > Gulberg > Shalamar > Data Ganj Baksh. Fish samples from the Allama Iqbal zone had a 65.10% lower plate count compared to those from the Nishter zone. Highest total coliform count (53.6 ± 26.85 MPN.g⁻¹) was found in samples from Allama Iqbal zone and lowest (10.02 ± 2.15 MPN.g⁻¹) in fish from Aziz Bhatti zone. In comparison to total coliform, highest average fecal coliform and *E. coli* count was recorded in fish from Gulberg zone (60.51 ± 49 . MPN.g⁻¹ and 36.03 ± 25.58 MPN.g⁻¹ respectively). The appreciable disparities in fish quality across six zones of Lahore highlight the influence of geographic location on microbial contamination. Notably, these findings highlight the need for targeted interventions in specific zones to improve fish safety, including enhanced training for vendors and stricter enforcement of hygiene standards.

Figure 3: Comparison of microbial parameters of fish collected from two types of vendors. [a] Total Plate Count, [b] Total coliform, fecal coliform and *E. Coli*

Figure 3 shows a comparison of the microbial parameters of fish collected from the superstores and traditional vendors. Total Plate Count for the fish sourced from traditional vendor was ≈ 150 times higher than those purchased from superstores (Figure 3a). In the case of total coliform, the count was

similar for the fish sourced from two different types of retailers (Figure 3b). However, the counts of fecal coliform and *E. coli* in samples collected from superstores were 63.52% and 58.61% higher, respectively, than those in samples purchased from traditional vendors (Figure 3b).

Table 1: Microbial quality of the fish collected from markets of Lahore (Mean $\pm$ SE)

Species	TPC (cfu.g ⁻¹)			
	Mean	SE	Min	Max.
<i>L. rohita</i>	10.80 x 10 ^{3a}	5.96 x 10 ³	0.59 x 10 ³	93.0 x 10 ³
<i>O. niloticus</i>	8.86 x 10 ^{3a}	3.78 x 10 ³	0.22 x 10 ³	42.0 x 10 ³
<i>W. attu</i>	5.24 x 10 ^{3a}	1.80 x 10 ³	0.24 x 10 ³	22.4 x 10 ³
	TC (MPN.g ⁻¹)			
<i>L. rohita</i>	41.73 ^a	17.22	3.6	240
<i>O. niloticus</i>	12.26 ^a	2.14	<3.0	>1100
<i>W. attu</i>	31.71 ^a	10.95	9.2	160
	FC (MPN.g ⁻¹)			
<i>L. rohita</i>	11.38 ^a	4.70	<3.0	75
<i>O. niloticus</i>	5.12 ^a	0.80	<3.0	11
<i>W. attu</i>	26.54 ^a	14.93	<3.0	210
	<i>E. coli</i> (MPN.g ⁻¹)			
<i>L. rohita</i>	19.88 ^a	6.96	3.6	93
<i>O. niloticus</i>	7.67 ^a	1.51	<3.0	15
<i>W. attu</i>	50.68 ^a	32.03	3.6	460

Similar alphabets as superscript in the same column indicate nonsignificant difference among fish samples ($p > .05$).

DISCUSSION

Foodborne illness defined by the World Health Organization as “a disease of infectious or toxic nature, caused by, or thought to be caused by, the consumption of food and water”, is caused by a wide range of agents (Baird-Parker, 2016). Fish, being rich in nutrients and moisture, provides an ideal environment for microbial growth. The number of spoilage microorganisms increases significantly during improper transportation and storage conditions, which is especially problematic given the highly perishable nature of fish. Without proper handling and storage, microbial contamination can rapidly escalate, leading to spoilage and potential health hazards (Dilmaçunal & Kuleaşan, 2018). To prevent spoilage and ensure the quality and safety of fish products, it's crucial to maintain optimal postharvest conditions, including adequate refrigeration, minimal handling, and strict hygienic practices (Nie et al., 2022).

Coliforms, an important group of the family Enterobacteriaceae are considered as bacterial indicators of sanitary quality of food. *Escherichia coli*, the most significant member of the Enterobacteriaceae family, is a universal resident of the human intestine and primarily a facultative anaerobe. Fecal coliforms are well known to contribute to fish spoilage and cause illness in both humans (Patel et al., 2014). Infections from coliforms are transmitted through contaminated fish, and coliform counts serve as indicators of potential fecal contamination, reflecting the hygiene standards maintained during food preparation. Improper processing, handling, and storage of fish can significantly increase contamination levels, thereby compromising fish quality and safety.

At the time of harvest, the microbial load of the fish normally varies from 10^2 to 10^5 cfu.g⁻¹ (ICMSF, 1986). In present study, total microbial load of about 40.0 – 83.33 % of fish samples collected from each zone showed total plate count in the range of 10³ -10⁴ cfu.g⁻¹. However, the microbial load of any fish sample did not exceed the permissible limit of 5×10^5 cfu.g⁻¹. The admissible limit for total coliform, fecal coliform and *E. coli* is <100 MPN.g⁻¹, <10 MPN.g⁻¹, and <500 MPN.g⁻¹ respectively (ICMSF, 1986). Our results showed that total coliform count was higher than the permissible limit in 9.30% of the total fish samples.

The presence of these microorganisms reflects poor hygiene practices during post-harvest handling of fish. Fecal coliform was higher than permissible limit of >10 MPN.g⁻¹ in 53.45% of the samples. *E. coli* count did not exceed limit of 500 MPN.g⁻¹ in any of the samples. Higher microbial load of the fish samples collected from the traditional vendors in comparison to superstore indicate improved storage conditions and fish handling at the latter premises. Nevertheless, higher fecal coliform count of the fish sourced from superstore

indicate that these market settings also need to improve hygiene practices in the fish supply chain.

Earlier studies on the microbial quality and safety of fish available in the commercial markets of Lahore, Pakistan, are meager. Nevertheless, studies in various regions have indicated the potential of food safety issues for the fish available in the commercial markets. Chatta et al., (Chatta et al., 2018) reported increase in microbial load of fish as it moved from primary to secondary retailers in the supply chain in Lahore and attributed it to poor hygienic conditions in the fish markets. The authors reported that aerobic plate count in samples of *Labeo rohita* and *Ctenopharyngodon idella* collected from retailer shops (2.25×10^6 cfu.g⁻¹ and 4.82×10^6 cfu.g⁻¹) were significantly higher than the samples collected from main fish market (1.22×10^6 cfu.g⁻¹ and 1.12×10^6 cfu.g⁻¹).

Sarkar et al. (2020) determined the bacterial contamination of Nile tilapia samples collected from super shops and local market of Dhaka, Bangladesh. The authors reported that all the fish samples were found to be contaminated with *E. Coli*, *Shigella spp.*, *Salmonella spp.* and *Vibrio spp.* Mitiku et al. (2023) determined the occurrence and microbial load pattern along the fish origin food value chain in upper Blue Nile watershed, Ethiopia. The authors reported an average total coliform count of 1.2×10^2 cfu.g⁻¹ and 5.10×10^4 cfu.g⁻¹ in cooked and raw fish samples, respectively. Alkuraieef et al. (2021) evaluated microbiological quality of fish sold in Saudi Arabian markets and found that microbial load was higher than permissible limit in some of the samples.

The findings of the present study have significant implications for public health and food safety in Lahore. The detection of elevated levels of total coliform, fecal coliform, and the presence of *E. coli* in fish samples from both local markets and superstores indicates the need for improved sanitation and hygiene practices throughout the fish supply chain.

CONCLUSION

The results of present study reveal the need for improvement of hygienic condition in fish supply chain in district Lahore, Pakistan. Variation in microbial quality of fish collected from different zones and vendor types suggest inconsistent handling and storage practices. Future research should continue to explore the factors contributing to microbial contamination in fish, facilitating the development of effective interventions to protect consumer health in Lahore and beyond.

Conflict of Interest

Authors declare no conflict of interest for this study.

Funding Information

This study did not receive funding from any source.

REFERENCES

- Alkuraieef, A. N., Alsuhaibani, A. M., Alshawi, A. H., Alfaris, N. A., & Aljabryn, D. H. (2021). Chemical and microbiological quality of imported chilled, frozen, and locally cultured fish in Saudi Arabian markets. *Food Science and Technology*, 42, e52520. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1590/fst.52520>
- AOAC. (2023). *Official methods of analysis of aoac international* (18th ed.). Gaithersburg, Md. AOAC International.
- Baird-Parker, A. C. (2016). Food poisoning: Tracing origins and testing. In B. Caballero, P. Finglas, & F. Toldrá (Eds.), *Encyclopedia of food and health* (pp. 72-76). Burlington, United Kingdom. Academic Press.
- Chatta, A. M., Khan, M. N., Mirza, Z. S., Ali, A., & Yaqub, S. S. (2018). Microbial quality of farmed fish in markets of lahore, pakistan: A health concern. *Pakistan Journal of Agricultural Sciences*, 55(4), 921-927. doi: <http://doi.org/10.21162/PAKJAS/18.4991>
- Dilmaçunal, T., & Kuleşan, H. (2018). Novel strategies for the reduction of microbial degradation of foods. In A. M. Grumezescu & A. M. Holban (Eds.), *Food safety and preservation. Modern biological approaches to improving consumer health* (pp. 481-520). London. Academic Press.
- FAO. (2022). *The state of world fisheries and aquaculture. Towards blue transformation*. Rome, Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, Rome.
- FDA. (2023). *Bacteriological analytical manual*. Available Online. U.S. Food and Drug Administration. Retrieved from <https://www.fda.gov/food/laboratory-methods-food/bacteriological-analytical-manual-bam>.
- Hasselberg, A. E., Aakre, I., Scholtens, J., Overå, R., Kolding, J., Bank, M. S., . . . Kjelleevold, M. (2020). Fish for food and nutrition security in ghana: Challenges and opportunities. *Global Food Security*, 26, 100380. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gfs.2020.100380>
- ICMSF. (1986). *Microorganisms in food 2. Sampling for microbiological analysis: Principles and specific applications* (2nd ed. Vol. 5). Toronto, Canada. University of Toronto Press.
- Ljusenius, Å., Lovatelli, A., & Qabeel, B. (2020). The international year of artisanal fisheries and aquaculture is coming up in 2022. *FAO aquaculture newsletter* (62), 13-15.
- Maulu, S., Nawanzi, K., Abdel-Tawwab, M., & Khalil, H. S. (2021). Fish nutritional value as an approach to children's nutrition. *Frontiers in nutrition*, 8, 780844 doi:<https://doi.org/10.3389/fnut.2021.780844>.

- Mitiku, B. A., Mitiku, M. A., Ayalew, G. G., Alemu, H. Y., Geremew, U. M., & Wubayehu, M. T. (2023). Microbiological quality assessment of fish origin food along the production chain in upper Blue Nile watershed, Ethiopia. *Food science & nutrition*, 11(2), 1096-1103. doi:<http://doi.org/10.1002/fsn3.3147>
- Nie, X., Zhang, R., Cheng, L., Zhu, W., Li, S., & Chen, X. (2022). Mechanisms underlying the deterioration of fish quality after harvest and methods of preservation. *Food Control*, 135, 108805. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodcont.2021.108805>
- Patel, A., Singhania, R., Pandey, A., Joshi, V., Nigam, P., & Socko, C. (2014). Enterobacteriaceae, coliforms and *E. coli*. In C. A. Batt & M. L. Tortorello (Eds.), *Encyclopedia of food microbiology* (2nd ed., pp. 659-666). Amsterdam. Academic Press, Elsevier, Ltd.
- Sarkar, S., Dey, S. K., Nipu, M. A. I., Brishti, P. S., & Billah, M. B. (2020). Microbiological assessment of Nile tilapia *Oreochromis niloticus* collected from different super shops and local market in Dhaka. Bangladesh. *Journal of Fisheries*, 8(2), 784-791. doi:<http://doi.org/10.17017/j.fish.153>
- Shafi, J., Waheed, K. N., Zafarullah, M., Mirza, Z. S., & Yaqoob, S. S. (2020). Effect of icing on quality of silver carp during frozen storage. *Journal of Food Processing & Preservation*, 44(9), e14654. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/jfpp.14654>
- Sharif, M., Azam Niazi, M., & Jabbar, A. (2014). Seafood exports: Challenges and way forward. *Pakistan Journal of Agricultural Research*, 27(4).
- UNICEF. (2021). The state of food security and nutrition in the world 2021. Retrieved from: <https://data.unicef.org/resources/sofi-2021/>